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**ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ КОНСТИТУЦИЯЛАРИ ВА САЙЛОВ ҲУҚУҚИ
ТАРИХИДАН (Туркистон АССР, Хоразм ХСР, Бухоро ХСР ва Ўзбекистон ССР
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АННОТАЦИЯ

Мақолада Ўзбекистон Республикаси мустақилликка эришгунга қадар амалда бўлган конституциялар тарихи ёритилган. Унда конституциялардаги сайловлар билан боғлиқ бўлимларига асосий эътибор қаратилган бўлиб, мавжуд тузум ва даврлардаги сиёсий жиҳатлар, сайлов жараёнлари билан боғлиқ масалалар таҳлил қилинган. Шунингдек, конституциялардаги синфий муносабатлар хусусида маълумотлар келтирилган.

Калит сўзлар: конституция, совет ҳукумати, курултой, халқ нозирлари совети, сайлов, сайлов ҳуқуқидан маҳрум қилиш, овоз бериш, ҳақсизлар.

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**КОНСТИТУЦИИ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН И ИСТОРИЯ ИЗБИРАТЕЛЬНОГО
ПРАВА (На примере конституций Туркестанской АССР, Хорезмской ССР, Бухарской
ССР и Узбекской ССР)**

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье освещается история конституций Республики Узбекистан до обретения страной независимости. В ней основное внимание уделяется разделам конституций, связанным с выборами, анализируются политические аспекты настоящей системы и периода, а также вопросы, связанные с избирательным процессом. Кроме этого, освещаются вопросы, связанные с информацией о классовых отношениях содержащейся в конституциях.

Ключевые слова: конституция, советская власть, курултай, совет народных назиров, выборы, лишение избирательных прав, голосование, лишены.

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THE CONSTITUTIONS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN AND THE HISTORY OF VOTING RIGHTS (On the example of the constitutions of the Turkestan ASSR, Khorezm SSR, Bukhara SSR and the Uzbek SSR)

ABSTRACT

The article highlights the history of the constitutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan before the country gained independence. It focuses on electoral sections of constitutions, analyzes the political aspects of the present system and period, and issues related to the electoral process. In addition, issues related to information about class relations contained in the constitutions are highlighted.

Index terms: constitution, Soviet power, kurultai, council of people's Nazirs, elections, deprivation of voting rights, voting, disenfranchisement.

1. INTRODUCTION

Every child of the country wants to carefully study all the realities of his homeland from the history of his homeland. Therefore, it is our main duty to our people to deeply and objectively cover the experiences of our people, the fate of our compatriots and the history of the roads we have traveled until we reach such bright days as today. With the following information, we will try to shed light on the political aspects of the current system and period, focusing on the sections of the history of the Constitutions in force in our independent homeland to date, related to the electoral system. The Constitution is the basic law of the state, which determines the structure of the state, the system of government and administration, their powers and the order of formation, the electoral system, the rights and freedoms of citizens, as well as the judiciary. In other words, the Constitution is the basis of all existing laws and the most basic feature of statehood [2].

2. RESEARCH METHODS

“Every state, while choosing its path of independence and development, enshrines in its Constitution - the Basic Law - the most important goals and objectives that serve the well-being of the people. Consequently, a country with a Constitution that is in harmony with the will, language and good intentions of its people will never deviate from the lofty goals it has set, but will always move forward”[1].

When we look at the history of the constitution of our country, first of all, “Temur’s rules” appear before our eyes. In turn, the “Temur’s rules” have the character of a special form of constitutional document typical of the civilization of Eastern and Asian countries, which, along with Sharia law, had a strong impact on the fate of the peoples of Central Asia. The famous Russian scholar D. Logofet studied the “Temur’s rules” and praised it as the Constitutional Code of Turkestan, which emerged 500 years before Europe, in other words, the Constitution of the reign of Amir Temur. From time immemorial, it has been known that a work is very valuable in essence, and in practice, many copies have been copied and distributed. “Temur’s rules” is an important guide for the crown princes. That is why most of the rulers copied this work, kept it in their personal library and used it as an important guide in the political activities of the state.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Shah Jahan (1628-1657), a descendant of our great compatriot Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, ordered the skilled secretaries of Kokand khan Muhammad Alikhan (1821-1842) and the Emir of Bukhara Abdulahadkhan (1885-1910) to copy for themselves the “Temur’s rules”.

After the declaration of independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the world community, from the first constitution of the Turkestan ASSR to the Constitution adopted at the eleventh session of the Supreme Soviet of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 8, 1992. We must emphasize that it has a history of excess constitutions.

After the February Revolution of 1917, the network of Soviets of Workers', Soldiers' and Peasants' Deputies in Russia grew rapidly. In May 1917 the First Congress of the Peasants' Soviets was held, and in June the First Congress of Workers and Soldiers. The Second Congress of the Soviets of Workers and Soldiers Deputies, which opened on October 25 of this year, announced that all power had passed into the hands of the Soviets. The Third All-Russian Congress of Soviets, held in January

1918, adopted two acts of constitutional significance. This important document was the Declaration on the Rights of Workers and Exploited People and the Resolution on Federal Institutions of the Russian Federation [3. p. 244].

Before that, if we look briefly at the history of Russian constitutions, the first constitution dates back to the reign of Emperor Alexander I (1777-1825). The draft “State Charter of the Russian Empire” was developed. However, this bill was rejected by the emperor. The next attempt at a constitution was made by Alexander II (1818-1881), and in 1881 the Minister of the Interior, Count MT Loris-Melikov (1824-1888), presented to the emperor the Loris-Melikov Constitution, which he had developed. This draft was usually to be approved by the emperor and put up for discussion by the council of ministers. However, on the same day, Alexander II was killed by terrorists of the “People’s Will” (“People’s Will”). On April 29, 1881, Alexander III (1845-1894) drafted the Manifesto on the Inviolability of Autocracy, which was immediately repealed by the Loris-Melikov Constitution. By 1905, the next Russian emperor, Nicholas II (1868-1918), had issued the Supreme Manifesto for Improving Public Order.

After the Bolsheviks came to power, one of the main problems they faced was to create a new form of statehood in the country. In this regard, the development of a new management system has become one of the priority tasks to be addressed. In line with the existing revolutionary tradition and ideas about the essence of the new government, the Soviet republic was seen as the ideal of the political system. In this connection, since 1918, the Soviet state has held almost every year Soviet re-election campaigns, which have become a broad form of involving the country’s citizens in state building.

The constitution of the RSFSR, adopted in 1918, legitimized the dictatorship of the urban and rural proletariat and the poor peasantry as a republic of Soviets of Workers, Soldiers and Peasants’ Deputies, and took over all local authorities. The regional, provincial, district, and volost congresses of the Soviets were declared their highest authority in the region. According to paragraphs 24 and 30 of Chapter 6 of Section 3 of the Constitution, the highest authority in the RSFSR belonged to the All-Russian Congress of Soviets, and in the inter-congress period to the All-Russian Central Executive Committee of the Soviets.

The Constitution of the Turkestan ASSR, adopted on October 15, 1918, is recognized as the first encyclopedia in the history of our country. The constitution of the RSFSR was the basis for the creation of this constitution and was discussed by the special commission of the Turkestan Central Executive Committee at the VI Congress of Soviets of the Turkestan ASSR on October 5-14, 1918. The Constitution consisted of 6 sections, 15 chapters and 60 paragraphs.

I - Declaration of the Rights of the Working and Exploited People.

II - General provisions of the Constitution of the RSFSR

III - The beginning of the main

IV - The structure of Soviet power

V - Active and passive suffrage

VI - About the budget and finance

Sections 1 and 2 of the Constitution were copied from the Constitution of the RSFSR, in which all the territories occupied by the Russian state were henceforth declared the Soviets of Workers’, Soldiers’, Sailors’, Cossacks’ and Peasants’ Deputies as the Russian Socialist Federal Soviet Republic has been shown [7].

In terms of the structure and content of the Constitution of the Turkestan ASSR, Turkestan is an Autonomous Soviet Socialist Republic. Also, the powers of the Turkestan ASSR in other areas were given very broadly, which did not correspond to the concept of an autonomous republic at all, because by this time the civil war in Russia had temporarily strained relations with Turkestan [8].

In order to strengthen the new social, economic and political system in Turkestan, the Constitution provides for the establishment of internal affairs, justice, labor and social security, foreign affairs, military affairs, education, post and telegraph, railways, agriculture, food, state control, national affairs, strengthened the People’s Commissariats, such as the Central Council of National Economy, by the force of law. Unfortunately, a large part of the local population was not

able to get acquainted, at least in general, with the main document defining the state structure of the country. The reason was that it had not been published in the local languages. In this document, the Soviet-style “self-determination” did not change the colonial status of the local population in Turkestan.

The second constitution of the Turkestan ASSR was approved by the IX Congress of the Turkestan ASSR on September 24, 1920, in which sections 1 and 2 were devoted to the Declaration of the Rights of Workers and Exploited People and the General Provisions of the Constitution of the RSFSR. Section 3 deals with the social and state rights of the Turkestan ASSR and its relations with the RSFSR.

Both of the above constitutions, in terms of their structure and content, defined the exploitation of humanity and the abolition of private property as the main task of the young Soviet state, as well as the establishment of the victory of socialism in all countries. The right to vote and stand for election was granted to citizens over 18 years of age. Persons earning money from hired labor, those living on non-wage income, traders and intermediaries, clergy, gendarmerie officers, and police and security officials were disenfranchised.

In addition, there is almost no significant difference in the sections on “active and passive suffrage”. Only Chapter 13 of the 1918 constitution, entitled “Elections to Soviets and Congresses,” was divided into separate sections in the 1920 constitution, and the term of office of deputies was extended from three to six months. The number of deputies for those living in villages, auls and settlements has been increased from 30 to 50. The number of deputies nominated to the congresses of regional and district councils from city and village councils has also changed dramatically.

According to these constitutions, all those living in the Republic of Turkestan of the RSFSR who have reached the age of 18 before the election day, regardless of religion, nationality, place of residence, are entitled to vote and stand for election to the Soviets, industry, trade, agriculture and all other categories of workers, servicemen; Soviet Army and Navy soldiers;) however, it was noted that local Soviets could lower the age limit set by the Central Government of the Republic of Turkestan with respect to all citizens who had lost their ability to work to a certain extent. However, no comment or instruction was given on the issue of restoring the rights of the “disenfranchised” who were deprived of the right to vote to participate in the elections [10].

In this regard, it should be noted that in the history of the constitutions in force in the territory of modern Uzbekistan, the constitutions of Khorezm and Bukhara People’s Soviet Republics, which were formed after the overthrow of the Khorezm (Khiva) Khanate and the Emirate of Bukhara, have a special place.

The first Constitution, adopted at the First Congress of All-Khorezm Soviets of the Khorezm SSR (April 26-30, 1920), for the first time in the centuries-old history of Khorezm reflected the political rights of the broad population and proclaimed democratic freedoms.

The leadership of the USSR tried to function as an independent state in accordance with its constitution. According to the constitution, the new state was divided into 22 districts. In late April and early May 1920, district councils of these districts were formed, in each of which 5-7 council members were elected. Soviets were elected in 14 Uzbek, 5 Turkmen, and three Kazakh and Karakalpak districts, and elders were elected in each district. The Constitution consists of 13 chapters and 37 articles, and includes the structure of state and local authorities, the social system and the rights and freedoms of citizens, and the procedure for holding elections to the Soviets. The Soviets were temporarily allowed to exercise their right to vote in the elections, along with the common people, as well as traders and priests.

The constitution declared the property of the khan and his relatives to be state property. It was also allowed to use the means of production as private property, and the right to free circulation of money was defined as unlimited.

This constitution was drafted against the nation-state system, and in the first stage of the establishment of Soviet power allowed the private ownership of the country's means of production, private ownership of land, its sale, and the right of everyone to free use of their wealth. On the other hand, this constitution officially declared the name of the Khiva state as Khorezm, leaving the name

of the city center, Khiva, unchanged. The Congress of People's Deputies is the highest body of power in the republic, and is convened once a year, and, if necessary, at the request of local Soviets, until the end of the year.

In addition, the Congress of People's Deputies elected the Khorezm Council of People's Ministers, a government that has the right to govern the republic and resolve all relevant issues until the next convocation. All state bodies and people of the republic are subordinated to this Council of People's Ministers. The Council of People's Ministers was responsible to the Congress of People's Deputies and reported on its activities to the Congress.

The Council of People's Ministers consisted of 15 members - the chairman, the first deputy chairman, the second deputy chairman, 2 secretaries and inspectors of military, justice, economic affairs, control, agriculture, finance, health, social security, education and foreign affairs. In accordance with the instructions given by the Council of People's Ministers in accordance with the election law, the district councils (shura) were formerly called "Qala" and were elected by the locals to govern the adjacent territories. Everyone over the age of 18, regardless of religion, nationality, tribal affiliation or gender, has the right to vote and be elected to the Congress of People's Deputies and local Soviets, and all people are recognized as equal.

Counter-revolutionaries, traitors who oppose freedom and the interests of the people, the mentally ill, usurers, those convicted of crimes, khans and khans' descendants, those who oppose the constitution and those who violate the rights of minorities are deprived of the right to vote and stand for election. On the contrary, foreigners who supported the world revolution and the Khiva revolution and proved their loyalty to it had the right to vote.

The Central Election Commission (CEC) was set up by the Council of People's Ministers to conduct the elections and sent local election commissions to their places. The CEC submitted a report to the Council of People's Ministers on the results of the inspection of the mandates of the people's representatives. Re-elections were held if the CEC made its decisions on dubious mandates and the authority of the representative was not confirmed. If it is determined that the election was held in general wrong, the issue of calling a second election was considered by the Council of People's Ministers and another date for convening the Congress was set [13].

It is characteristic that in all 4 Congresses held by the All-Khorezm Soviets during 1920-1923, a new constitution was adopted each time. While many new clauses were forcibly added to the text of the new constitution adopted by the Second Congress (May 15-23, 1921) under pressure from the Turkic Commission, the Constitution adopted at the Third Congress (July 23, 1922) set the program for the struggle for socialism and expanded these processes.

At the IV Congress (October 17-20, 1923) the Khorezm People's Soviet Republic was transformed into the Khorezm Soviet Socialist Republic (USSR). The new Constitution, consisting of 5 sections, 12 chapters and 44 articles, was adopted, which legitimized the transition of the state to the path of socialist development [11].

The Constitution of the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic, adopted at the II Congress of All-Bukhara Soviets on September 18-23, 1921 consists of an introduction, 5 chapters, 16 chapters and 79 articles. The participation of all representatives was emphasized. Freedom of private property and trade were reflected. The system established in Bukhara was a people's democratic republic. The constitution of the Bukhara SSR gave all citizens equal political rights and eliminated national inequality. According to the Constitution, the supreme body of the Bukhara SSR was the All-Bukhara Congress of People's Deputies, which consisted of 350 members, one representative for every 2,000 voters. The congress was convened once a year and considered important issues such as the adoption of the republic's constitution, amendments, government reporting and approval of the state budget.

According to the Constitution, the supreme legislative and supervisory body between congresses is the All-Bukhara Central Executive Committee. However, the constitution was amended in September 1923 to bring it into line with Soviet standards. Because the Bolshevik government in Russia was constantly pressuring the government of the USSR. On June 3, 1923, a group of commissions from Moscow expressed dissatisfaction with the work of the USSR government and the need to accelerate "socialist change". The influence of the Communists in the Bukhara government

grew, and the government was replenished with “experienced Soviet officials”. As a result, at the V Congress of All-Bukhara People’s Deputies held on September 18-20, 1924, the Bukhara Soviet Socialist Republic was transformed into the Bukhara Soviet Socialist Republic. The formation of the BSSR was an event artificially carried out by the communists. As a result, the democratic path of development was rejected and the “socialist direction” was chosen.

In the recognized constitutions of the Khorezm SSR and the Bukhara SSR, in contrast to the Constitution of the Turkestan ASSR, we can see that the attitude towards the category of “unjust” deprived of the right to vote is different.

In particular, the Constitution of the USSR differs from other constitutions in that the right to vote and stand for election is granted to citizens over 20 years of age.

Additional comments were also made as a note to the category of persons deprived of the right to vote in Article 58, paragraph “g” (“large landowners and capitalists”) and paragraph “d” (“relatives of emirs and former high-ranking officials of the Emirate”). In particular, the property qualification that determines whether a person belongs to a group of large capitalists or landowners is defined only in the General Regulations on Elections developed by the All-Bukhara Central Executive Committee (CEC) and the former Bukhara officials has been shown to be able to restore suffrage by a special resolution of [15]. Similarly, the restoration of suffrage is reflected in the constitution of the Khorezm SSR [16].

By 1924, the above three republics were completely abolished, divided into their territories, and all existing constitutions were repealed. On January 31, 1924, the first constitution of the USSR was adopted. The main document of the new state consisted of two sections: the “Declaration on the Establishment of the USSR” and the “Treaty on the Establishment of the USSR”.

The Declaration strengthened the dictatorship of the proletariat, shaped the labor rights of workers and peasants, as well as the class rights of workers. Russia (RSFSR), Ukraine (Ukrainian SSR), Belarus (BSSR) and Zakavkazye “Transcaucasia” (ZSFSR) established the unification into one union state, their territorial integrity, a single monetary system, a single union and at the same time the citizenship of each republic.

The supreme bodies of the Union were responsible for regulating all important areas of the state’s foreign and domestic policy, including the representation of the USSR in international relations, changing external borders, admitting new republics to the Union, and leading the Armed Forces.

However, the constitution did not provide for any information on the electoral system, the conduct of elections, the right to vote or deprivation of the right to vote. These processes were later reflected in the constitutions of the allied republics.

It is also noteworthy that after the adoption of the first constitution of the USSR, new constitutional processes throughout the allied republics did not begin immediately. If we do not take into account that the previous constitutions of some allied republics remained in force until 1926-1927, it would be more accurate to say that a constitutional gap was observed in the interim period.

The first draft constitution in the history of the Uzbek SSR was approved by the Second Congress of Soviets of Uzbekistan on March 27-31, 1927 and published on July 11. This Constitution, as well as the constitutions of other republics of the Union, stipulates that the powers of state power are “exercised by the deputies of the Soviets of Workers’ Peasants and the Red Army”. Uzbekistan included the Autonomous Republic of Tajikistan. The Tajik ASSR was given many powers, and a special section was devoted to relations between them. In order to make its constituent republics more dependent on the Center, the USSR has always considered disputes between them in its policy, starting with their constitutions and laws. The Tajik ASSR, which was part of Uzbekistan, was given the right to form and amend its Council of People’s Commissars at any time, to reconsider and approve laws passed by the Uzbek SSR, and many other powers.

Chapter 6, Chapters 8 and 9 of the Constitution are devoted entirely to the organization and conduct of elections to the Soviets. The designation was emphasized. In 1931, in connection with the separation of the Tajik ASSR from the Uzbek SSR, it was republished with amendments to the constitution. However, both constitutions do not address the issue of restoring the rights of citizens

deprived of the right to vote [28. p.30]. Only the Program of the Central Election Commission of the Uzbek SSR of December 12, 1927 “On elections to the Soviets” and 1929 “On elections to the Soviets of the Uzbek SSR” described citizens who did not exercise the right to vote and indicated the procedure for restoring their rights.

In particular, as former police officers, prison officials, etc. (Article 38, paragraphs “m” and “l” of this Program), Article 93 of the Constitution of the Uzbek SSR “a”, “b”, “v”, “g” and “d”) provided that persons deprived of their suffrage were now engaged in productive and socially useful work and had proved their allegiance to the Soviet government, their suffrage could be restored by a special decision of the Presidium of the Executive Committee of the USSR.

In the autumn of 1935, the USSR Central Executive Committee set up a constitutional commission chaired by IV Stalin to develop a new edition of the USSR Constitution that should reflect the idea of the victory of socialism. On June 12, 1936, the draft Constitution was published and discussed for six months at the republican congresses of the Soviets, starting from the meetings of workers at enterprises at all levels. On December 5, 1936, the VIII Extraordinary Congress of Soviets adopted the new Constitution of the USSR, which was historically sealed as the “Stalin Constitution”.

The Constitution consolidated theses on the leading role of the Communist Party, introduced norms defining the economic foundations of socialism, new chapters on the 1924 Constitution - social structure, local government, the judiciary and the prosecutor's office, the basic rights and obligations of citizens, the electoral system and the right to vote. suffrage was the prerogative of the constitutions of the republic). It also abolished all restrictions on suffrage enshrined in previous constitutions, demonstrating that suffrage is equal for all citizens [4].

For its time, the 1936 Constitution was very democratic, but the realization of the rights and freedoms proclaimed in it was not guaranteed by the current legislation, and the policy of mass repression pursued by the authorities was completely contrary to the basic legislation of the country. After the implementation of this constitution, new constitutional processes began throughout all the allied republics, just like the constitution of 1924.

In accordance with the “Stalin Constitution”, the second constitution of the Uzbek SSR, adopted on February 14, 1937 at the VI Extraordinary Congress of Soviets of Uzbekistan, was in force for more than 40 years. The Constitution consists of 13 chapters and 146 articles, Chapter 11 is devoted to the “Electoral System”.

The Constitution states that “elections of working people’s deputies to the Supreme Soviet of the Uzbek SSR, the Supreme Soviet of the Karakalpak ASSR, districts, districts, cities, villages and auls - by secret ballot by voters on the basis of universal, equal and direct suffrage”. (Article 133) All citizens of the Uzbek SSR who have reached the age of 18, regardless of generality, race and nationality, religion, education, place of residence, social origin, property status and past activities, have the right to participate in elections, deprived of the right to vote only by a court. with the exception of persons with disabilities and mental retardation (Article 134).

The next constitution, adopted by the Supreme Soviet of the USSR on October 7, 1977, was called the Brezhnev Constitution. This document went down in history as the “constitution of advanced socialism”, as it provided for the establishment of a “developed socialist society” and a “nation-state” in the USSR.

Despite its affiliation with previous constitutions (1918, 1924, 1936), this 1977 document represents a high level of constitutional legislation. The document defines new forms of “direct democracy” - public hearings and referendums, as well as new civil rights: the right to appeal against the actions of officials, the protection of honor and dignity through the courts, the right to criticize the actions of citizens. For the first time, the rights to health, housing, cultural achievements, and creative freedom were guaranteed.

On April 19, 1978, at the sixth extraordinary session of the Supreme Soviet of the Ninth Convocation of the Uzbek SSR, the third constitution of the republic was adopted in accordance with the Constitution of the USSR, which came into force on October 7, 1977. The Constitution consisted of 11 sections, 21 chapters and 183 articles. Unfortunately, many legal issues enshrined in both the

1977 Constitution of the USSR and the 1978 Constitution of the Uzbek SSR, including freedom of speech and the press, remained only a declaration in the current state system and one-party political system. Although the housing program was also widely included in the constitutions, it was not fully implemented and remained a major problem.

The last constitution of the Uzbek SSR also set out the rules for the exercise of Soviet power and the supreme goal of the working class, the peasantry, to build a communist society. For example, in the introductory part of the constitution, “the people exercise state power through the Soviets,” the “leadership and leadership of the communist party in public life” is often described.

The constitutions adopted for more than 70 years contain beautiful words about the people’s power, but in practice the provincial, district, city, village and township councils formed by the Communist Party’s programs and plans have no significance in the life of the society and state. not [8].

4. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, although all the constitutions adopted before independence were aimed at guaranteeing the basic law of the state, state structure, system of government and administration, the rights and freedoms of citizens, in fact, the constitutions adopted first in the RSFSR and then in the USSR were Bolsheviks. The creation of a new form of government in the Soviet Union, along with other allied republics, served to strengthen the dependence of Uzbekistan on the center. In this regard, the Soviet election campaigns, which have been held almost annually since 1918, serve as a basis for attracting the citizens of the country to state-building.

The Soviet state established in its constitutions the exploitation of humanity and the abolition of private property as its main principles, and devised a policy of deprivation of the right to vote in order to implement these principles. In this way he managed to restrict all the rights of a conscious, independent-minded population of the population, which could be opposed to colonial policy, and then to annihilate them with a policy of repression.

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